

EFFECT OF DIETARY SUPPLEMENTATION OF CARROT (DAUCUS CAROTA), A CAROTENOID SOURCE, ON GROWTH, SURVIVAL AND PIGMENTATION OF FRESHWATER ORNAMENTAL FISH, ORANGE MOLLY (POECILIA SPHENOPS, VALENCIENNES, 1846)

Rajendran Srinivasan* & Tanmoy Jana**

Department of Fisheries Science, School of Marine Science, Alagappa University, Karaikudi, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract:

Daucus carota (Carrot) peel, a protein-carotenoids complex, can provide antioxidants and carotenoids to ornamental fish diets. Fading ornamental fish are uninteresting to buyers. In this 45-day feeding trial, the effect of carrot peel extract on growth, coloration, antioxidant enzymes and immune response in Orange Molly (*Poecilia sphenops*) was examined. Five diets were created: one control (C), one commercial feed without carotenoid sources, and three experimental pelleted diets with 1% Treatment (T1), 3% Treatment (T2) and 5% Treatment (T3) powdered carrot meal. After the experiment, the fish's skin and muscle carotenoid content and Specific Growth Rate (SGR) were measured. Skin and muscle carotene ($\mu\text{g/g}$ wet weight basis) increased significantly. Digital photo analysis shows T3 has the most colour intensity, followed by T2, T1, and C. T3 had the highest Body Weight Gain (BWG)%, SGR%, and Food Conversion Ratio (FCR) growth (252.80, 2.952, 0.854), while C had the lowest (110.28 percent and 1.802). Carrot peels powder at 1%, 3% and 5% ensured 100% fish survival, while C and T4 at 90% and 80%, respectively. Carrot peel powder at 5gm/100gm fish feed had the highest pigment concentration in fresh fish muscles and a higher SGR. T3 fish had higher respiratory burst activity, indicating higher immunity. This study showed that ornamental fish farmers should use carrot peel-incorporated feed to improve growth, coloration, antioxidant activity and profit.

Key Words: Antioxidant, Carrot Peel, Feed Supplement, Ornamental Fish, Orange Molly

1. Introduction:

The hobby of keeping aquariums is gaining popularity in India, which ranks among the emerging nations. The brilliant hues, flamboyant patterns, and overall stunning appearance of ornamental fishes have garnered them a lot of attention over the years (Pandey and Mandal et al., 2017). The rate of success of the ornamental fish trade will be very high if the color of the fish is more vibrant (Sudirman et al., 2020). Therefore, there is a causal relationship between the consumption of carotenoids and the coloration of fish (Halten et al., 1997). Carotenoids are the pigments that give ornamental fish their distinctive colours, both on the surface of their bodies and in their muscles. In addition, to its function as a pigment in the body, it also serves as a precursor for transcription regulators, as an antioxidant, and as a factor that contributes to the body's immune system. These additional functions are very important for the visual effects that it produces (Bendich and Olson et.al., 1989). Additionally, it has been discovered that fish with a high carotenoid content have a greater resistance to diseases caused by bacteria and fungi (Wagde et al., 2018).

Because of this, pigmentation is a significant criterion for fishes because it has an impact on their acceptability in the commercial sector. There are many different kinds of synthetic sources as well as natural sources, such as plants and animals, which are present for the supply of carotenoids. However, synthetic carotenoids are currently on the market and while they are available to buy, their prices are very high and their application in the aqua feed industry is restricted due to species specificity (Torrissen and Naevdal, 1984). Carrot has excellent antioxidant property The present study was designed to assess the dietary efficacy of carrot (*D. carota*) meal on survival, growth and pigmentation, antioxidant and immune response of Orange molly *P. sphenops*, (Valenciennes, 1846) as Molly fish can able to adjust to any adverse climatic condition, easy to cultivate and breed in captive condition. Due to the unique properties of carrot, the present study was designed to assess the dietary efficacy of carrot (*D. carota*).

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1 Experimental Site:

The experiment was carried out in the Department of Fisheries Science, School of Marine Sciences, Alagappa University, Science Campus, Karaikudi, Tamil Nadu, India.

2.2 Collection and Acclimatization of Fishes:

A total 100 experimental fishes including males and females of orange molly *P. sphenops*, of more or less uniform size (3.5 ± 0.01 cm in length and 0.8 ± 0.02 gm in weight) group was purchased from commercial ornamental fish. Initial disinfection of fishes followed by salt treatment (5%) and bath treatment with KMnO_4 solution @ 1 ppm for 3 to 5 minutes (Bakshi et. al., 2018). During acclimation, fish were fed with control food diet @ 2% of the body weight which is readily available in market (Behera et. al., 2018).

2.3 Experimental Design and Setup:

After proper acclimatization of one-week, healthy fishes were stocked into the experimental tanks for feeding experiment. Prior to the experiment start day, fishes were starved for 24 hrs. and the total length and plus weight were measured. A total 10 set of cleaned, disinfected glass aquarium tank of 50 L capacity ($39 \times 37 \times 35$ cm) were used for 5 experiment groups (G-I:C, G-II: T1, G-III: T2, G-IV: T3, G-V: T4) with replicate. In each tank 10 numbers of juveniles were reared and the total experiment was conducted for 45 days. Fishes were fed twice a day during morning 10:00 hrs. to afternoon 16:00 hrs. Equivalent to 2.0 % of their body weight. The physico-chemical characteristics of water sampled from all the tanks throughout the experimental period were assessed by the standard methods of APHA (2012) on daily basis and weekly basis (Table 1).

2.4 Experimental Feed Preparation:

The experimental feed was prepared with basic ingredients such as Corn flour, Rice flour, Egg yolk, Fish meal and Vitamin mixture and Wheat flour was used as feed additive. In all experiments the same feed was used except for the incorporation of carotene. All ingredients were split into 5 equal parts. Then it was oven dried at 45°C for 48 hours and then the contents were powdered with the help of a grinder and sieved in particle size of 0.1 to 0.2 mm, afterward stored in the refrigerator at 4°C . The dried powdered carrot meal was incorporated to the diets just before palletization at the rate of 0, 1, 3, 5 g/ 100 g of feed (Feed type C, T1, T2, T3 respectively) for the experiment and no carrot powder is added to the T4 feed because it is fully commercial feed (Table -2). The feeds were prepared after every fortnight to avoid fungal infection and pigment loss due to storage and amount of feed was adjusted at every sampling (fortnightly interval) according to increase in fish weight.

2.5 Feeding Experimental Diet:

The control fish group were fed with customized formulated diet C (without addition of the powder of *D. carota*), experiment G-I fed with diet T1 ($T1 = C + 1\text{g}/100\text{g}$ powder Denote - [RF - Rice Flour, CF - Corn Flour, WF - Wheat Flour, FM - Fish Meal, MP - Milk Powder, GP - Allium sativum (Garlic) Powder & TP - Curcuma zedoaria (Turmeric Powder), MV - Multi Vitamin] of *D. carota*), experimental G-II fed with diet T2 ($T2 = C + 3\text{g}/100\text{g}$ powder of *D. carota*), experimental G-III with diet T3 ($T3 = C + 5\text{g}/100\text{g}$ powder of *D. carota*) and experimental group IV were fed with diet T4 ($T4 =$ commercial diet (CD) - Optimum micro pellet, Made in Thailand). All fishes were fed at the rate of 2% percent of their body weight twice a day with experimental diets. Daily rations were adjusted every two weeks according to fish body weight in each of the tanks. Optimal daily feeding rates for *P. sphenops* may vary due to protein requirements and varies with the rearing environment as well as their genetic composition and feeding rates (% BWG/day) which was determined based on the recommendations of different researchers.

2.6 Proximate Composition Analysis - AOAC (2004):

Proximate analysis of feed, and tissue are performed as per the prescribed method of AOAC (2004). Crude protein, carbohydrate, lipid, ash content and moisture were estimated.

2.6.1 Estimation of Moisture (Uzma Shabir 2018):

In general samples were taken and heat for 105°C for 16 hr. or 125°C for 4 hrs. or 135°C for 3 hrs. in hot air oven. Remove the Petri dish from the oven and keep it in desiccator for 1 hr.

2.6.2 Estimation of Crude Ash (CA) AOAC (2004):

About 1.5 to 2g sample to be taken in the silica crucible and keep it in muffle furnace and keep it in muffle furnace and incinerate at $550 - 600^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h. Collect the crucibles from furnace and keep it in desiccators until completely cooled. Weight the ash content accurately.

2.6.3 Estimation of Total Lipid (TL) AOAC (2004):

Ten gram of the minced sample was taken for both fish and feed.

2.6.4 Estimation of Protein and Carbohydrate:

Protein content of feed (Khanizadeh et al., 1995) and fish tissue was measured by Lowry's Method (Lowry et al, 1951) and Carbohydrate content of fish muscle and feed was measured by Anthrone Method (Loewus, 1952)

2.7 Feeding Behavior Analysis:

The feeding behavior was categorized according to the responses recorded by Lee and Mayer's (1997) with modification.

2.8 Growth Study:

Growth performance and nutrient utilization of experimental fishes were evaluated by following equation:

$$1 \quad \text{BWG (\%)} = \frac{\text{Final weight (g)} - \text{Initial weight (g)}}{\text{Initial weight (g)}} \times 100$$

$$2 \quad \text{LG (\%)} = \frac{\text{Final body length (cm)} - \text{Initial body length (cm)}}{\text{Initial body length (cm)}} \times 100$$

$$3 \quad \text{Survival rate \%} = \frac{\text{Initial fish number} - \text{Final fish number}}{\text{Initial fish number}} \times 100$$

$$4 \quad \text{CF} = \frac{\text{Wet weight of the body (g)}}{[\text{Standard body length (cm)}]^3} \times 100$$

$$5 \quad \text{SGR (\%)} = \frac{\ln \text{Final body weight} - \ln \text{initial body weight}}{\text{Number of culturing days}} \times 100$$

$$6 \quad \text{FCR} = \frac{\text{Total amount of feed given (g)}}{\text{Total weight gain (g)}}$$

2.9 Estimation of Carotenoid Content in Different Tissues of Fish and in Experimental Diet:

The carotenoid content was measured by the method of Bendich and Olson (1979). The optical density was read at 380nm, 450nm, 475nm and 500nm in a double beam microprocessor UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Model - LI-2802R). The wavelength, at maximum absorption, was used for the calculation.

2.10 Water Quality Analysis:

The different types of physicochemical parameters of water were analyzed by standard method (APHA, 1995)

2.11 Statistical Analysis:

The data were statistically analysed by one way ANOVA and Regression Test by using the software statistical package IBM SPSS version 26 and Microsoft Excel 2016 and data were subjected to one way analysis of variance and Duncan's multiple range tests were used to determine the significant differences if any, between the means. Comparisons were made at the 5% probability level.

3. Result & Discussion:

Poecilia sphenops prefer hard water with a pH range of 7.5-8.2 and the ideal temperature range for them is 18°C to 28°C Tamaru et.al. Vali et. al. 2002 initially maintain the water temperature, pH and ammonia i.e. 27 ± 1 °C, 7 - 7.8 and < 0.02 mg/L respectively and as well as maintain the water hardness around 200 mg CaCO₃ before the initiation of the toxicity experiment on adult common molly (P.sphenops). Wagde et. al. Reported that temperature fluctuate between 22.94°C to 23.60°C, pH belongs to 7.6 - 8.2, Oxygen range from 5.4 - 7.1 mg/L with the alkalinity range of 300 - 340 mg/L was ideal for the growth and coloration study on swordtail (Xiphophorus hellerii). The water quality results in the current study show that the water in the experimental tanks is hard, with a temperature and pH in the ideal range. During the experimental trial the temperature and pH was maintained between 27 °C to 32 °C and 7.9 to 8.7 respectively. Average DO value (5.7 - 6.5 mg/L) was maintain during the experimental period and other parameters like Total Hardness (TH), Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, ammonia, alkalinity were respectively maintained in favourable condition which were suitable for the growth of the fish and are shown in the (Table 1).

The proximate composition of feed showed that all the experimental feeds were as per the nutritive profile of their respective feed formula (Table 3). The proximate composition of experimental feed showed higher carbohydrate content than commercial feed and moisture and ash content were relatively less than commercial feed. It is observed that the commercial feed slightly induces the biochemical parameters of the experimental fishes than the commercial fish feed (Table-4).

During introduction of feed into the different fish tanks the behavioral changes of experimental fishes was observed. At the very early stage from the first day upto the 7th day of experiment the fishes take 5 to 11 mins to fully complete the food. As the day increases the acceptance of the food also increases and the feeding time also decreases. After 7th day the rejection limit also very low. So it implies that due to new environmental condition fishes take time to finish their feed but after acclimatizing with the new environment it takes only 1 to 2 min. to finish the experimental feed. During the initial period of the experiment the feed acceptance (Figure 1) time was long but at the time increasing the acceptability of the feed increasing and the rejection percentage also decreasing. The feed was considered rejected only if the feed was uneaten by fish after 30 min to 1 hrs. At the beginning of the experiment the rejection percentage was maximum 5% but day by day it was gradually decrease.

Growth study was done by calculating the initial and final growth parameters during the experiments by measuring the SGR (Specific Growth Rate), FCR (Food Conversion Ratio), and % BWG (Body Weight Gain), % LG (Length Gain) (Table- 5, 6, 7). Fish growth efficiency was shown to be higher when the FCR value was lower. The FCR levels in this recent study differed from species to species. *P. Sphenops* FCR levels range from 1.0 to 1.1 when carrot powder is added to the meal. According to Fry et al. 2018, the FCR value of fish is between 1.0 and 2.4. The values of the Feed Conversion Ratio showed a reduction for fish fed with Diet T3, but fish fed with diet T1, T2, and T4 showed higher values, when compared to those fed with Diet T3. Devi et al. 2019 reported that black molly attain better growth but FCR value was low when they fed formulated feed incorporated with spirulina, carrot powder and beetroot powder and this formulated can replace the cost effective commercial feed. Maiti et al. 2017 conclude that in common carp the percentage of growth was high in the group that fed formulated feed incorporated with carrot peel powder other than tomato peel powder. A correlation test between the growth parameters (log of body weight and log of body length) resulted as illustrated in (Figure 2). Logarithmic value of the body weight was positively related with logarithmic value of the body length of *P. sphenops* showing a slope of $Y = 1.745x - 0.8912$ and $R^2 = 0.7346$. Zutshi and Madiyappa 2020 found that body weight of the *P. sphenops* correlated positively with body length, with a slope of $R^2 = 0.8727$ when fed with Lantana. camara flower petal incorporated in formulated diet. In X. hellerii Zutshi and Madiyappa 2020 showed better growth ability ($P < 0.05$) fed with the formulated diet with carotenoid pigment present in *L. camara*. Tiewsoh et al. 2019 reported that in goldfish diet with 6% carrot is more effective for growth and colouration. CF values in experimental groups, when compared to the control groups, were insignificantly different, but fish fed with diet T3 showed higher values, when compared to those fed with T1, T2, T4 and control group. In this study the regression result shows that at the 95% confidence level $P < 0.05$. So, the growth is allometric growth as b value is $\neq 3$.

Carotene level in fish skin observed visually (Figure 7) and at four different wavelengths. At 380 nm, the total variance in skin carotenoid levels was determined. The overall variation in carotenoid level of skin was observed at 500nm was ranged from 0.68 to 2.6 μ g/g. A maximum amount of carotenoid was recorded in 5g/100g followed by 3g/100g carrot powder incorporating diet fed fish and minimum level of carotenoids was seen in 1g/100g carrot and control diet fed fish.

At the end of experiment, it was evaluated that carrot powder incorporated diet T3 significantly showed highest carotenoid concentration ($P < 0.05$) in the skin of *P. sphenops* at 475nm wavelength whereas absence of carrot powder in diet (control) caused a significant reduction of carotenoid concentration (Figure 3-6). But the commercial feed has also the significant role for colour enhancement. According to the result it is observed that more than 1g carrot powder can enhance the fish body coloration significantly. Few studies have shown and demonstrated the effect of natural carotenoids on the survivability, growth, colour development and antioxidational responses in ornamental fishes but some drawbacks also there. While plant meal contains certain imbalanced amino acids, it slows down the growth of the fish. Baron et.al. (2008) tried beet root juice on *Colisalalia*, but it didn't improve the fish's skin colour or growth. In this investigation, it was also discovered that if the carrot augmented feed did not store adequately, the carotene level of the feed decreased. Among natural vegetables, carrot (family Apiaceae) is a root vegetable which is one of the important pigment source that rich in bioactive compounds. In the carrot root the total carotenoid content present in the edible portion ranging from 6-55 mg/100g Simon and Wolff, (1987) with β -carotene (44-79 % of total carotenoids, 5.3 - 10 mg/100 g) as major component and the most important thing is that it is the single major source of β -carotene providing 17% of total vitamin A.

5. Conclusion:

As a result, the research discovered that using a vegetable carotenoid source (such as carrot) had a lot of favorable benefits on the colouring of mollies. However, while they are inexpensive and widely available, it appears that processing them into a raw material is useful (powdering after drying) before adding them to feeds is important to produce more good results. As a result, "carrot powder can be used as a colour enhancer and growth promoter in the orange molly diet at a rate of 5%."

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Table 1: Water Quality Parameters

Parameters	Range
Temp.(°C)	27-32
pH	7.9-8.7
DO (ppm)	5.7-6.5
TH (ppm)	190 – 197
Ca ²⁺ (ppm)	50-57
Mg ²⁺ (ppm)	13.32-16.32
NH ₃ (ppm)	0.001-0.005
ALKY (ppm)	80-92
SAL ‰	0.036-0.045

Table 2: Formation of Experimental Diets, (Ingredients in gm/100gm)

Ingredients	Treatments / in gram				
	C	T1	T2	T3	T4
RF	25	25	25	25	25
CF	20	20	20	20	20
WF	10	10	10	10	10
FM	24	24	24	24	24
Egg Albumin	9	9	9	9	9
MP	10	10	10	10	10
GP & TP	1	1	1	1	1
MV Mixture	1	1	1	1	1
Total	100	100	100	100	100
Dried Carrot Powder	-	1	3	5	-

Denote - [RF - Rice Flour, CF - Corn Flour, WF - Wheat Flour, FM - Fish Meal, MP - Milk Powder, GP - Garlic Powder & TP - Turmeric Powder, MV - Multi Vitamin]

Table 3: Proximate composition of experimental feeds

Composition	C	T1	T2	T3	T4
Carbohydrate (%)	42.2	42.2	42.2	42.2	35
Protein (%)	30.4	33.3	32.3	34.5	23
Fat (%)	10.5	14.5	14.5	14.6	13
Moisture (%)	10.5	10.7	10.6	10.6	13
Ash (%)	5.2	6.2	6.3	5.1	11

Table 4: Proximate composition of experimental fishes

Composition	C	T1	T2	T3	T4
Carbohydrate (%)	15.2	15	15.2	16.2	16
Protein (%)	21	22.3	23.2	23.5	22
Fat (%)	11.2	11.2	11.2	11.2	13
Moisture (%)	10.5	10.7	10.6	10.6	13
Ash (%)	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2

Table 5: Growth study of the experimental fish

Treatment	Weight (gm) (± SD)	% Body Weight Gain	Length (cm) (± SD)	% Length Gain	SGR (%)
Initial	0.85 ± 0.59		3.64 ± 0.63		
C	1.8 ± 0.59	110.28	4.6 ± 0.63	26.37	1.802
T1 (1g/100g)	2 ± 0.44	133.64	4.9 ± 0.38	34.62	1.774
T2 (3g/100g)	2 ± 0.44	133.64	4.8 ± 0.38	31.87	1.928
T3 (5g/100g)	3.02 ± 0.42	252.8	5.8 ± 0.23	59.34	2.952
T4	2.45 ± 0.25	186.21	5.2 ± 0.23	42.86	2.225
Commercial feed					

Table 6: FCR value of the experimental fishes

Treatment	FCR
C	1.053
T1	1.036
T2	1.045
T3	0.854
T4	1.154

Table 7: CF value and % Survivability of the experimental fishes

Treatment	Condition Factor	% Survivability
C	0.976	90
T1	0.971	100
T2	1.007	100
T3	1.093	100
T4	1.073	80

Figure 1: Length weight relationship

Figure 2: Logarithmic relationship between length and weight

Figure 3: Estimation of carotenoid concentration in 380nm

Figure 4: Estimation of carotenoid concentration in 450nm

Figure 5: Estimation of carotenoid concentration in 475nm

Figure 6: Estimation of carotenoid concentration in 500nm

Figure 7: colour enhancement of the *P. sphenops*

